

IMPROVING THE VAT ADMINISTRATION SYSTEM IN UKRAINE TOWARDS ADAPTATION TO EUROPEAN STANDARDS**Sushkova O.**

*PhD (Economics), Associate Professor,
Associate Professor for the Department of Customs and Commodity Science,
State Tax University (Irpin, Ukraine);
Guest researcher, the Institute for Austrian and International Tax Law,
Vienna University of Economics and Business (WU)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878310>*

Abstract

In the article it was investigated the functioning mechanism of e-invoicing in Ukraine, which made it possible to identify key problematic areas in its work. Taking into account the European integration path of Ukraine, the European rules for the VAT administration were studied, as well as the best practice of the e-invoicing operation among the EU Member States was investigated. Taking into account European standards and best practices, ways for improving e-invoicing in Ukraine were outlined.

Keywords: VAT, invoice, tax administration, e-invoicing, validation

1. Introduction.

Value added tax is a key element of the tax system of Ukraine. This, on the one hand, is due to its fiscal significance for the budget of Ukraine, because this tax ranks first in the structure of tax revenues and ensures the accumulation of more than 30% of the revenue part of the consolidated budget of Ukraine. And on the other hand, the biggest tax gaps in the Ukrainian economy are specific to VAT, which is the result of the presence of a large number of schemes for minimizing and evading the payment of this tax. According to experts' estimates, the Ukrainian budget does not receive about UAH 30 billion annually due to the existence of fraudulent VAT schemes, and the most widespread scheme called "scrolls" ranks fourth in terms of the level of influence on the amount of tax revenues in the budget of Ukraine [25].

However, one of the most effective tools for reducing VAT gap and combating VAT fraud is the efficient operation of the VAT administration system. As the world practice proves, VAT has a sizeable fiscal potential, thanks to which it can allow the accumulation of additional tax revenues in the budget and reduce tax gaps with VAT, only at the expense of increasing the efficiency of the system administration of VAT, without increasing the tax rate [27, p. 8]. At the same time, the effective functioning of the administration system is considered mainly from the point of view of the widespread use of modern digital technologies, which allow reducing the influence of the human factor on decision-making on both sides – the tax administrations and taxpayers – and ensure tax compliance. In this case, the applying of an automated VAT administration system becomes of practical importance.

The automated VAT administration system, which includes the operation of the Unified Register of VAT invoices and adjustments calculations to them (hereinafter referred to as the Unified Register), has been used in Ukraine since 2011. During its operation, this system has undergone thousands of improvements and changes, but despite this, the system still has a large number of shortcomings and debatable points, which

cause taxpayers to be dissatisfied with its use and increase the number of conflicts (court cases) between taxpayers and tax administrations. At the beginning of 2023, the State Tax Service of Ukraine again made changes to the procedure for the functioning of the Unified Register, but they mostly have "cosmetic" role and do not fundamentally transform the VAT administration procedure in Ukraine, leaving controversial issues.

Besides that, undergoing numerous changes to the procedures of the VAT electronic system in Ukraine does not contribute to the improvement of its work and has a destructive effect on the business activity of taxpayers, a number of VAT administration procedures are at odds with the key principles provided for by the EU tax law, in particular for VAT. Since the declaration of independence, Ukraine has chosen the European integration path of development and the European standards became future guidelines for the development and functioning of the Ukrainian economic system, in particular the tax system. On the other hand, Ukraine received the status of a candidate for the EU membership in 2022, thus intensifying the process of integration into the EU. So, the prospect of future integration dictates the need for maximum approximation (adaptation) of the Ukrainian public administration system and in particular a tax administration system, to the European standards and practices. However, every large-scale innovation in the tax system or the tax administration system leads to certain losses for both the state (in the form of uncollected tax revenues, budget expenditures for financing changes in the tax system, etc.) and taxpayers (fines in the first the period of operation of new rules, costs for adapting technical capabilities to new requirements, etc.). Therefore, in order to minimize the deadlines and probable consequences (financial losses) from reforming and adapting the system to new rules after Ukraine acceded to the EU, we believe that it would be rational if Ukraine already starts the process of improving its VAT electronic administration system to bring it closer to the standards and principles of operation of a similar system in the EU.

2. Goals, Objectives and Methodology.

Due to the above arguments, the goal of the article is to determine proposals to improve the work of the electronic VAT administration system in Ukraine, taking into account the EU standards.

To achieve this goal, several scientific tasks have been solved in this article. We carried out a critical analysis of the work of the electronic system of VAT administration in Ukraine and in particular the automated system of registration of VAT invoices and adjustment calculations. It helped identify the key shortcomings in its work. Also, we investigated the main provisions of the EU VAT Directive, key principles of building the EU tax system, and the existing practice of VAT administration in the EU, as well as the results of use of the electronic invoice registration system in some EU Member States.

The results of these two analyses allowed the author to identify the key problematic issues in the work of the electronic system of VAT administration in Ukraine and inconsistencies with the main principles of VAT taxation in the EU. Regarding each point of problematic questions, we formulated proposals for improving the Ukrainian VAT administration system, especially in terms of registration of VAT invoices, to adapt it and bring it closer to European standards.

3. Results.

3.1. Characteristics of the systems of electronic VAT administration in Ukraine.

The electronic system of VAT administration was introduced in Ukraine in 2011 in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 1246 dated 29.12.2010 "On approval of the Procedure for maintaining the Unified register of VAT invoices", which defines the mechanism for entering information contained in the VAT invoice or calculating adjustments to the Unified Register [28]. According to this mechanism, the VAT taxpayer independently prepares a VAT invoice or the calculation of adjustments in electronic form in accordance with the standard approved by law and sends it for registration in the Unified Register. After the VAT invoice is received by the tax administration, the following aspects are deciphered and checked in an automated mode:

- compliance with the VAT invoice with the approved format (standard);
- the validity of the qualified electronic signature,

the procedure for its imposition, and the availability of the right to sign such VAT invoice by an official of the taxpayer;

- registration of the person who sent the VAT invoice for registration as a VAT taxpayer at the time of drawing up and registering such VAT invoice;

- compliance with the requirements established regarding the terms of adjustment of the amounts of the VAT obligations and VAT deductions (Article 192.1 and Article 201.10, Tax Code of Ukraine [33]);

- the presence of errors when filling in the mandatory details;

- availability of the appropriate amount on the special VAT account (the limit for registering a VAT invoice), calculated by Article 200^{1.3} and 200^{1.9} of the Tax Code of Ukraine ¹;

- availability in the Unified Register of information contained in the VAT invoice, which is being adjusted;

- the fact of registration/suspension of registration/refusal to register a VAT invoice with the same details;

- if there are grounds for stopping the registration of VAT invoices (risk monitoring).

The VAT administration system in Ukraine also provides for the VAT taxpayer to open a special electronic account at the State Treasury Service of Ukraine for VAT accounting. Thus, since 2016, by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 1177 dated 30.12.2015 [23], the State Treasury Service of Ukraine, based on the Register of VAT Taxpayers data, automatically and free of charge opens an electronic VAT account for each VAT taxpayer. The electronic VAT accounts are used for the automatic debiting of VAT amounts payable by the VAT taxpayer to the country's budget based on the results of its activities during the reporting month. At the same time, the payment of fines and penalties is made by the VAT taxpayer from the taxpayer's bank account. In case of cancellation of the registration of a VAT taxpayer, the State Treasury Service of Ukraine based on updated data in the Register of VAT Taxpayers automatically closes the VAT account of such a taxpayer and transfers the remaining funds to the country's budget.

Transfer of the amount of VAT payable by the VAT taxpayer based on the results of the month reporting to the country's budget takes place automatically

¹ The VAT taxpayer has the right to register tax invoices in the Unified Register for the amount of VAT (indicator $\sum \text{Invoice}$), calculated according to the following formula:

$$\sum \text{Invoices} = \sum \text{InvoicesIn} + \sum \text{Customs} + \sum \text{Replenishment} + \sum \text{Overdraft} - \sum \text{InvoiceOut} - \sum \text{Refund} - \sum \text{Excess}.$$

$\sum \text{InvoicesIn}$ - the total amount of VAT according to the tax invoices received by the VAT taxpayer, registered in the Unified Register.

$\sum \text{Customs}$ - the total amount of VAT paid by the VAT taxpayer during the import of goods/services to the customs territory of Ukraine and is determined based on the data of customs declarations.

$\sum \text{Replenishment}$ - the total amount of replenishment of the electronic VAT account from the current account of the VAT payer. This amount is reduced by the amount of excess balances on the electronic VAT account, which were returned to the current account of the VAT taxpayer in accordance with

the application submitted by him (but only until this indicator reaches zero).

$\sum \text{Overdraft}$ - the sum of the average monthly amount of VAT amounts that were declared by the payer to be paid to the budget for the last 12 reporting months and repaid (in installments, deferred). This indicator is subject to automatic recalculation every quarter.

$\sum \text{InvoiceOut}$ - the total amount of VAT according to tax invoices issued by the VAT taxpayer, registered in the Unified Register.

$\sum \text{Refund}$ - the total amount of VAT declared by the VAT taxpayer before the budget refund.

$\sum \text{Excess}$ - the total amount of the excess of tax liabilities, indicated by the VAT taxpayer in the VAT reporting submitted to the tax authority, over the amount of VAT indicated in the tax invoices drawn up by such taxpayer, registered in the Unified Register.

based on the data of the VAT reporting submitted by him. If on the date of submission of the VAT reporting, the balance of funds in the electronic account of the VAT taxpayer exceeds the amount of VAT payable to the budget, the taxpayer has the right to submit, as part of this reporting, an application for the transfer of the such balance of funds to the bank account of this VAT taxpayer. If there are not enough funds in the electronic account, the VAT taxpayer must transfer the insufficient funds from his own bank account to the electronic account before the deadline for the payment.

As can be seen from the list of directions for checking VAT invoices before their registration in the Unified Register, the conditional balance on the electronic account of the VAT taxpayer is used to determine the limit for registering a new VAT invoice². According to the formula for calculating this limit, if a VAT taxpayer applies for a VAT refund, this amount of the claimed refund reduces the amount of the limit for registration of VAT invoices. If the specified conditional balance (according to the calculation formula) on the electronic VAT account is insufficient during the registration of the VAT invoice, the VAT taxpayer can top

up this account. Accordingly, a VAT taxpayer who has applied for a VAT refund, but has not yet received this amount, will be forced to withdraw additional funds from circulation and transfer them to an electronic VAT account to ensure the registration of other VAT invoices and the fulfilment of obligations to their buyers. Although according to Resolution No. 1177 [23], the VAT taxpayer has the right to receive information from the tax administration about the status of his electronic VAT account (menu "Transaction Register") and the amount of VAT for which he has the right to register VAT invoices in the Unified Register using the information and telecommunications system "Electronic Cabinet", this procedure of registration of VAT invoices only burdens the mechanism of functioning of the electronic VAT administration system, creating both new obstacles for VAT taxpayers and new objects of control for tax administrations.

Risk monitoring involves an assessment of the riskiness of the VAT taxpayer according to established criteria³, an assessment of his tax history⁴, and an assessment of the degree of riskiness of the operation⁵

² See footnote 10 (index \sum Invoice).

³ Criteria for risky VAT taxpayer:

1. The VAT taxpayer was registered (re-registered) on the basis of invalid (lost) and forged documents according to the information available in the government authorities.
2. The VAT taxpayer was registered (re-registered) in the state registration authorities by natural persons with subsequent transfer (registration) to the possession or management of non-existent, deceased, missing persons according to the information available in the government authorities.
3. The VAT taxpayer was registered (re-registered) in the state registration authorities by natural persons who did not intend to conduct financial and economic activities or exercise powers, according to the information provided by such persons.
4. The VAT taxpayer was registered (re-registered) and conducted financial and economic activities without the knowledge and consent of its founders and legally appointed managers in accordance with the information provided by such founders or managers.
5. The VAT taxpayer – a legal entity does not have open accounts in banking institutions, except for accounts in Treasury bodies (except budget institutions).
6. The VAT taxpayer did not submit VAT tax returns for the last 2 reporting periods to the tax authority, contrary to the provisions of the Tax Code of Ukraine. (Clause 6 with changes introduced in accordance with Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 1428 of 12/23/2022)
7. The CIT payer did not submit financial statements for the last reporting period to the tax authority, contrary to the provisions of the Tax Code of Ukraine. (Clause 7 with changes introduced in accordance with Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 1428 of 12/23/2022)
8. The tax authority has tax information that became known in the course of the current activity during the performance of the tasks and functions assigned to the tax authority, which determines the riskiness of the transactions specified in the VAT invoice submitted for registration.

The VAT taxpayer receives a decision on compliance with the risk criteria of the VAT taxpayer through the Electronic Cabinet on the day of making such a decision.

⁴ VAT taxpayer has a positive tax history if one of the following criteria is met:

- 1) the amount of supply indicated by the taxpayer in the tax invoices registered in the Unified Register in the current month does not exceed UAH 1 million, provided that the amount of supply of goods/services in the current month in transactions with one recipient – the VAT taxpayer does not exceed UAH 100,000, and the manager – an official of such a VAT taxpayer is a person who holds a similar position in no more than three (inclusive) VAT taxpayers;
- 2) during any 4 reporting months out of the last 6, the taxpayer permanently registers invoices in the Unified Register for the supply of goods/services with the same product/service code in accordance with the UCG FT/DCGP;
- 3) the residual value of fixed assets for income tax payers at the end of the reporting period is more than UAH 5 million, provided that the manager and founder have not changed since the beginning of the previous year;
- 4) the presence of own (right of ownership / use), leased land plots of more than 200 ha inclusive or the presence of leased land plots of communal and/or state property with an area of at least 0.5 ha (as of January 1 of the current year), declared by 20 February of the current year;
- 5) for the last 12 months, the payment of a single insurance contribution per 1 employee exceeds the amount of the minimum wage by 2 times, provided that the manager and/or founder has not changed since the beginning of the previous year and the average monthly salary for the last 12 months the number of employees is at least 5 people;
- 6) the total amount of VAT and taxes and fees paid in the previous reporting year (except for the amount of import VAT) by the taxpayer and its separate divisions, which submitted the invoices for registration in the Unified Register, amounts to more than UAH 10 million.

⁵ Criteria for risky transactions:

1. The volume of the supply of goods/services, specified in the tax invoice submitted for registration in the Unified Register for increasing the amount of tax liabilities, is equal to or exceeds the value of the balance, which is defined as the difference between the volume of acquisition of such goods/services in the customs territory of Ukraine (except for the volume of acquisition of goods/services under transactions that are exempt from taxation and subject to taxation at a zero rate) or importation into the customs territory of Ukraine of such goods specified in the received tax invoices registered in the Unified Register, and customs declarations, increased by 1.5

for which the VAT invoice has been drawn up. However, it should be noted that by the Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 1428 dated 23.12.2022, VAT invoices for which the volume of supply does not exceed UAN 5,000 are excluded from the range of VAT invoices, which are subject to risk monitoring before their registration in the Unified Register.

According to the results of the verification of the information specified in the VAT invoice, which is registering, by the criteria indicated above, an electronic receipt is generated in an automated mode on the acceptance, non-acceptance, or stop of registration of the VAT invoice and is sent during the operating day to:

1) to the seller (supplier) and the buyer (recipient) at the same time – in case of registration of a VAT invoice;

2) to the VAT payer (supplier) – in case of non-acceptance of the registration of the VAT invoice. Such a receipt must contain a list of the reasons for such non-acceptance;

3) to the seller (supplier) and the buyer (recipient) at the same time – in case of stopping the registration of VAT invoice.

The information and telecommunications system "Electronic Cabinet" has a "Monitoring Invoice/AC" menu, which provides VAT taxpayers with access to the indicators used when the VAT invoices or AC registration is stopped in the Unified Register, namely:

1) *indicators D and P* – the indicators by which the Automated VAT Administration System varies the information provided by the VAT taxpayer and determines whether he can count on "immunity" from the blocking of VAT invoices. According to paragraphs 3

times, and the volume of supply of the corresponding goods/services specified in the tax invoices registered in the Unified Register. { Paragraph 1 in the wording of Resolution of the CM No. 1428 of 12/23/2022 }

2. Absence (cancellation, suspension) of licenses issued by licensing authorities certifying the right of the VAT taxpayer to manufacture, export, import and wholesale trade in excisable goods (products), in relation to the goods specified by the VAT taxpayer in the tax invoice submitted for registration in the Unified Register on the date of their completion.

3. Absence of information (up-to-date record) in the Unified Register of excise taxpayers on the sale of fuel on the date of drawing up the tax invoice in relation to the business entity that submitted the tax invoice for registration in the Unified Register, in which the goods (fuel) by codes according to UCG FT.

4. Compilation of the RK by the supplier of goods/services to the tax invoice drawn up for the recipient – the VAT payer, if a change in the nomenclature of the goods/service is envisaged (for goods by codes in accordance with UKTZED – change of the first four digits of the codes, and for services by codes in accordance with the State of the product and service classifier - the first two digits of the codes), provided that such a product/service is not specified in the RK submitted for registration in the National Tax Registry, in the data table of the VAT payer as a product/service that is supplied (provided) on an ongoing basis.

5. Exceeding the amount of compensation for the value of the goods/services specified in the calculating adjustment for the reduction of the amount of tax liabilities submitted by the recipient of such goods/services for registration in the Unified Register, over the amount of the balance, which is defined as the difference between the amount of purchase of such

and 4 of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 1165 dated 11.12.2019 [24], VAT invoices are not subject to monitoring and are subject to registration in the Unified Register (unconditional registration), if at the same time indicators D (an indicator of the actual total tax burden of the taxpayer) and P (an amount of VAT which registered for the current reporting month) have the following values: $D > 0.05$; $P < Pm \times 1.4$ ⁶.

2) *indicators of a positive tax history (PTH)* – a system of criteria for a positive tax history of a taxpayer ⁷, which is defined by the norms of the Annex to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 1165 dated 11.12.2019 [24].

However, it should be noted that within the functioning of the Ukrainian automatic system of VAT administration, there is a "section of work" that is performed by a special commission consisting of employees of the tax administration (at the regional level, in some cases at the central level). So, when according to the results of automated monitoring a VAT taxpayer who has drawn up and/or submitted a VAT invoice for registration in the Unified Register meets at least one criterion of the VAT taxpayer riskiness ⁸, or the operation of the taxpayer meets the riskiness criteria ⁹, the registration of such VAT invoice stops. Then, based on the additional information received (by means of electronic communication) at the request of the taxpayer, the above-mentioned commission makes a decision to exclude the VAT taxpayer from the list of risky or recognize the operation as not risky.

Documents accepted by the commission for consideration of the issue of excluding a VAT taxpayer

goods/services in the customs territory of Ukraine (except for the volume of acquisition of goods/services for operations that are exempt from taxation and subject to taxation at a zero rate), specified by the supplier in registered in the Unified Register, compiled for the recipient of such goods/services, and the volume of supply, reduced by 1.5 times and specified by the recipient of those registered in the Unified Register for the supply of such goods/services. {Paragraph 5 in the wording of Resolution of the Central Committee No. 1428 of 12/23/2022 }

6. Submitting for registration in the Unified Register the calculation of the adjustment for the reduction of tax liabilities to the tax invoice drawn up and registered by the supplier of goods/services to the non-VAT payer within a period exceeding 30 calendar days from the date of drawing up the tax invoice registered in the Unified Register without violating the limits the registration terms established by the Tax Code of Ukraine, except for the calculating adjustment to the tax invoice, which reflects transactions for the supply of electric energy (commodity subheading 2716 according to the Ukrainian Tax Code), the supply of natural gas (commodity subheadings 2705, 2709 and 2711 11 according to the Ukrainian Tax Code), the supply of heat energy (conditional product code 00401). {Paragraph 6 in the wording of Resolution of the CM No. 1428 of 12/23/2022 }

⁶ The Pm indicator is the largest monthly amount of VAT specified in tax invoices registered by the taxpayer in the Register for the last 12 calendar months preceding the month in which the invoice was drawn up.

⁷ See footnote 13 (Criteria for positive tax history of taxpayer).

⁸ See footnote 12 (Criteria for risky VAT taxpayer).

⁹ See footnote 14 (Criteria for risky transactions)

from the list of risk VAT taxpayers include: 1) contracts, in particular foreign economic contracts, with the annexes; 2) contracts, powers of attorney, acts of the governing body of the VAT taxpayer, which authorize persons who receive products in the interests of the VAT taxpayer to carry out the transaction; 3) primary documents regarding the supply/purchase of goods/services, storage and transportation, loading, unloading of products, warehouse documents (inventory descriptions), including invoices, acts of acceptance and transfer of goods (works, services) taking into account the existing typical forms and industry specifics; 4) settlement documents and/or bank statements from personal accounts; 5) documents confirming the conformity of products (declarations of conformity, quality passports, certificates of conformity), the availability of which is stipulated by the contract and/or legislation; 6) other documents confirming non-compliance of the VAT taxpayer with risk criteria. Within seven working days, based on the results of the review of the documents submitted by the VAT taxpayer, the commission decides to exclude him from the list of risky.

The content of additional information from the taxpayer to recognize the transaction as not risky is defined in Clause 13 of Order No. 1165 [24] and includes information on the types of economic activity carried out by the taxpayer, a list of product codes (according to the Ukrainian classification of goods of foreign economic activity) that the payer supplies, buys, or imports, and/or service codes (according to the State Classifier of Products and Services) provided, received, or imported by the taxpayer, with explanations and references to the taxpayer's VAT reporting. Based on this information, within five working days, the commission concludes the registration of the VAT invoice in the Unified Register or a complete refusal to register it.

As an exception to the general procedure, it is possible to automatically take into account the provided information only for two categories of VAT taxpayers: 1) according to clearly defined criteria producers of agricultural products that receive a budget subsidy; 2) VAT taxpayers for whom indicators $D > 0.02$, $P < P_m \times 1.4$ and who in the additional information indicated goods or services, the volume of supply of which according to the data of the Unified Register for the last 12 calendar months is more than 25% of the total volume of supply such taxpayer. Also, by Clause 22 of Order No. 1165 [24], the commission must automatically accept additional information from the taxpayer and accordingly decides regarding the registration of the VAT invoice in the Unified Register if the court decision annuls the commission's decision not to accept additional information from the taxpayer.

To illustrate the practical results of the functioning of such a "hybrid" (electronic with elements of manual control), we will provide statistical data on the administration of VAT in Ukraine. According to the official data from the State Tax Service of Ukraine [20], at the end of 12 months of 2022, there were 46,600 cases under consideration in courts of various instances for lawsuits against tax authorities in the amount of UAH 263.9 billion. At the same time, 8,400 cases were considered (18% of the total number of cases) for UAH

90.8 billion (34.4% of the total amount of all court cases), of which: were in favour of tax authorities – 3.2 thousand cases (including non-property disputes) (38.1% of the total number of cases considered) for UAH 36.7 billion (40.4% of the total amount of considered cases), and in favour of taxpayers – 5.2 thousand cases (61.9% of the total number of considered cases) for UAH 54.1 billion (59.6% of the total amount of considered cases). The majority of cases involving taxpayers' claims against tax authorities belonged to the category of cases on recognition of invalidity of tax notices-decisions on refusal to register a VAT invoice – 22.8 thousand cases (48.9% of the total number of court cases) for UAH 217.1 billion (82.2% of the total amount of the total number of court cases). However, 4,400 cases were considered (19.3% of the total number of court cases regarding the blocking of VAT invoice registration) for a total amount of UAH 55.2 billion (25.4% of the total amount of court cases related to blocking the registration of a VAT invoice), of which 2.2 thousand cases (50%) for UAH 31.1 billion (56.3%) were in favour of tax authorities. So as we can see, the electronic system of VAT administration in Ukraine, which is designed to simplify the process of tax administration, only creates additional conflicting issues, increasing mistrust among taxpayers in the tax administration and the tax system as a whole.

Thus, the Ukrainian VAT electronic administration system, on the one hand, is the first attempt to apply artificial intelligence in tax administration, and on the other hand, the VAT administration mechanism has a considerable element of manual management of the process of registering electronic invoices, which brings significant subjective (and means a possibly corrupt) aspect in the functioning of the system. In addition, the very mechanism of proving the transparency of the transaction, for which the VAT invoice is created, has a wide field for subjective (read corrupt) interpretation of the content or filling of "additional information" by employees of tax administrations. Such a functioning mechanism of the VAT electronic administration system completely defeats the purpose of tax administration automation in terms of minimizing the human (subjective) factor in decision-making by controlling bodies, increasing the objectivity and transparency of the tax administration system. This also affects the attitude of taxpayers to the tax system and tax administration of the country, determining the level of conscientious tax payment. As Shwabii K. says [29], taxes by themselves do not have a positive or negative colour, this colour is determined by the tax administration system and the mechanism of their budget distribution. Also, regarding the special VAT accounts, although they fulfil the role of guaranteeing the payment of VAT to the country's budget and minimize the fiscal risks of the state, but at the same time create additional obstacles for conducting business activities for VAT taxpayers (the VAT taxpayer withdraws part of the working capital to this account), violate rights and freedom (mobility) of taxpayers, which does not contribute to the formation of trust relations between VAT taxpayers

and tax administrations. This approach needs to be reviewed regarding the need for its application and/or improvement in accordance with European practice.

3.2. The VAT e-invoicing system in the European Union

3.2.1. General rules of the e-invoicing in the EU

The study of the European practice of e-invoicing was carried out in two directions – the identification of the key pillars of the EU legislation on VAT taxation and the main principles of the tax administration system, in particular in the field of VAT, and the key procedures that form the e-invoicing systems of individual Member States. This approach is due to the fact that the EU VAT legislation and principles of taxation form the framework in which the tax administration system of any Member State should function, and the procedures of tax administration reflect how in practice it is possible to ensure the achievement of tax goals within these frameworks.

The legal basis of VAT taxation in the EU is the VAT Directive [10], which regulates the procedure for determining the key elements of the VAT (taxpayers,

taxable transactions, exclusion from the list of taxable transactions, taxable amount, tax rates), rights and obligations of taxpayers and non-taxpayers, including regarding the procedure for issuing invoices, as well as the procedure for determining the place of implementation of taxable transactions, especially for cross-border transactions, and the mechanism for applying VAT taxation rules for special schemes and taxation regimes. Given the fact that the topic of this article is focused on the process of VAT administration, the investigation of the VAT Directive should be conducted with an emphasis on the rules for issuing VAT invoices and their validation by tax administrations. Thus, regarding the VAT invoicing process Articles 217-240 of the VAT Directive [10] provides a single set of basic EU-wide invoicing rules (Table 2). However, Member States have the possibility to deviate from the norms of the Directive under certain conditions and within certain limits to introduce special measures aimed at simplifying tax collection or preventing certain forms of tax evasion.

Table 2

EU invoicing rules according to the VAT Directive

Issue and content of invoices	Sending e-invoices and acceptance them by the tax administration	Storing e-invoices and access to them
<p>1) the taxpayer has the right to issue either a paper VAT invoice or an electronic one, provided that the recipient accepts them;</p> <p>2) electronic invoices are mandatory for the field of public procurement;</p> <p>3) the taxpayer is obliged to issue a VAT invoice when performing most types of B2B transactions (with VAT taxpayers or legal entities – non-VAT taxpayers). An exception for B2B transactions are transactions exempt from VAT (transactions for the provision of public services and activities according to Article 132 (1) of the VAT Directive and transactions for the provision of financial and insurance services according to Article 135 (1) of the VAT Directive;</p> <p>4) the taxpayer is obliged to issue a VAT invoice when carrying out some B2C transactions, namely when carrying out a distance sale with taxation in another EU country or the sale of a new vehicle with delivery to another EU country.</p>	<p>1) the taxpayers are free to send electronic invoices for an acceptance by a recipient;</p> <p>2) invoices are accepted by tax administrations, provided that the authenticity of the origin and the integrity of their content are guaranteed by one of two methods – either by using an advanced electronic signature or by electronic data interchange (EDI);</p> <p>3) in order to guarantee the authenticity and the integrity of e-invoices using EDI, member states may also, in accordance with the rules they established, require the sending of an additional final document on paper;</p> <p>4) Member States may not impose on taxable persons supplying goods or services in their territory any other obligations or formalities relating to the sending or making available of e-invoices.</p>	<p>1) the taxpayer independently chooses the format, method and place (any EU country other than the location of the VAT taxpayer) of storing VAT invoices;</p> <p>2) the authenticity of the origin and integrity of the content of the stored e-invoices, as well as their legibility, must be guaranteed throughout the storage period, as well as the information they contain cannot be changed and must remain legible throughout the storage period;</p> <p>3) the taxpayer may ensure the tax authorities have the access to e-invoices or information they contain without undue delay when they request it;</p> <p>4) the tax authorities in the Member State in which the taxpayer is established have the right to access, download and use e-invoices within the limits set by the rules of the Member State in which the taxpayer is established and in so far as those authorities require for the control purposes.</p>

Resource: create by author using [10; 26]

Comparing the norms listed in Table 2 with the norms of Ukrainian legislation in the field of VAT, it should be noted that the Ukrainian practice of issuing e-invoices fully complies with the EU rules and standards, but the procedure for sending e-invoices and especially their acceptance by the tax administration contains a number of discrepancies, namely: 1) e-invoices are accepted only after checking the riskiness of the taxpayer, his tax history (including payment of other taxes), his counterparty and transaction; 2) tax authorities have the right to request the provision of other tax information to confirm the validity of the e-invoice; 3)

the decision to register an e-invoice or not is made as a result of the work of a special commission of tax authority employees (subjective approach), and not based on objective signs or automatic/electronic tools for guaranteeing the validity and integrity of the invoice.

It should be noted that the preamble to the VAT Directive refers to a number of general principles by which national VAT taxation and administration systems should be formed (Fig. 1), namely: the principle of neutrality, the principle of efficiency, the principle of certainty and simplicity, the principle of effectiveness and fairness, and the principle of proportionality.

Fig. 1. Typology of EU VAT Principles [11]

The principle of neutrality comes from the very essence of VAT as a tax, namely from the thesis that the tax is paid by the final consumer and should not be paid at the intermediate stages of the path of this product or service to the final consumer, and accordingly Guideline 3 OECD, VAT collection should not affect the competitiveness of the taxpayer (both at the national level and at the level of the EU), distort their economic decisions [19, p. 7], prevents the free movement of goods and services [10].

In almost all court cases on VAT, the CJEU refers to the principle of neutrality, stating that the right to deduct VAT cannot be limited in any way provided that the taxpayer and/or the tax administration comply with all formal requirements for VAT [34]). Therefore, the right to a VAT deduction is a fundamental right of a VAT taxpayer, the violation of which leads to an increase in the costs of a business entity, a cascading effect, and as a result of this increase in the prices of goods or services of such a taxpayer, which in turn will start the process of increasing inflation, distort competition and will affect the economic growth [8, p. 22].

The principle of efficiency is that the costs of the taxpayer and tax administrations for compliance with tax law should be minimized as much as possible [19, p. 4].

The principle of certainty and simplicity provides the establishment of clear, transparent, and simple (understandable) tax rules so that VAT taxpayers have the opportunity to foresee the consequences of tax transaction and a certain mechanism for keeping records of tax transactions with VAT [19].

OECD Guidelines 2017 added to the list of VAT principles *the principle of effectiveness and fairness*, which provides for the establishment of such VAT rules that contribute to reducing the manifestations of VAT

fraud among taxpayers and at the same time correspond to the risks [18, p. 18].

The principle of proportionality is one of the key principles of European law which provides that the measures and instruments used by the EU Member States should not exceed the extent necessary to achieve the set goals. Based on the essence of this principle, there are certain limitations on the approaches used by tax administrations to combat fraudulent VAT schemes, namely they should not exceed (be tougher on taxpayers) the necessary level. Thus, Traversa E. and Ceci E. claim that guided by the principle of proportionality, tax administrations should not use tools to combat fraudulent VAT schemes, which provide a general presumption of fraud or strict liability of the taxpayer without any grounds for this (absence of the fact of using VAT evasion or avoidance scheme) and the possibility for the taxpayer to prove the legality of his actions [34].

Also among the key legal documents that regulate the process of issuing electronic invoices, we should single out Council Directive 2001/115/EC of 20 December 2001 amending Directive 77/388/EEC. The main view of the document is to simplify, modernize and harmonize the conditions laid down for invoicing in respect of VAT; businesses operating in EU Member States should have simplified invoicing regulations and procedures harmonized at the EU level [17, p. 340]. Also in 2014, the European Parliament approved Directive 2014/55/EU on electronic invoicing in public procurement [12]. It also takes steps to ensure the principles of equal treatment and technological neutrality run through e-invoicing [31], as well as ensuring general legal requirements and technical standards for business processes and interoperability at three levels: regarding invoice content (semantics), data format

(syntax) and method of transfer [12].

As for the e-invoices, e-invoicing is one of the areas where the EU Member States are aiming to achieve harmonisation, standardization of the mechanism and format of issuing them in order to ensure the possibility of using the system in any Member State. The ultimate goal is to simplify the implementation of cross-border sales operations. Thus, in order to improve the operation of the VAT administration system for business and strengthen the fight against VAT fraud, on December 8, 2022, the European Commission (EC) published the proposal on the EU VAT in the Digital Age (ViDA) reforms that includes three components with the timeline for 2023-2028 [2]. The main goal of this reform is to

harmonize Digital Reporting Requirements (DRR) and Continuous Transaction Controls (CTC) by EU states [5]. Other component is a transition of all EU Member States (from 2028) to electronic VAT reporting (e-reporting) in near-real-time format (within two working days after the event) based on electronic invoices (Fig. 2), which provides operation of a unified VAT invoices registration system across the EU [13]. The need for digitalization of the VAT administration system in the EU also arose due to the active growth rates of sales volumes of goods through various online platforms (especially such as platforms for short-term rental of housing or vehicles, etc.).

Fig. 2. EU requirements for VAT e-reporting that should be implemented by all Member States by 2028 [2]

However, the range of issues that still need to be decided include the following: 1) which periodicity (periodic (PTC) or continuous (CTC) type of transactions control to apply; 2) which reporting period is more suitable (quarterly or monthly for PTC, weekly or daily for CTC); 3) in what way to preserve the confidentiality of VAT taxpayer data, provided that a common system is used for all EU Member States; 4) what options should be provided for pre-filling VAT reporting; 5) what benefits from the use of the e-invoicing system must be provided for VAT taxpayers [16]; 6) what should include the definition of "substantial" and "formal" e-invoices data control.

3.2.2. The best e-invoicing practice of the EU Member States.

A number of EU countries have already implemented a system of electronic invoices. So **Italy** was one of the first European countries to introduce VAT e-Invoicing for B2G transactions in 2014. In March 2015, Italy introduced the official document exchange platform *Sistema di Interscambio (SDI)* and obligated all companies operating in Italy to generate electronic invoices by FatturaPA (XML) or other formats allowed by the European standard on electronic invoicing (EN 16931 [10]) and send them through SDI [35]. For now this system applies to invoicing for B2G, B2B and B2C (from January 2019) transactions, as well as transactions by "simplified scheme" and cross-border invoic-

ing (from January 2022). Micro-enterprises with revenues or fees of up to EUR 25,000 will be included in the e-invoicing scope of the application from January 2024. At the same time, due to the architecture FatturaPA XML can contain one or several (group) documents. Italy's electronic VAT administration system allows Italian tax administrations to verify tax transactions in real time.

During the process of registration of electronic invoices, their preventive verification is carried out according to formal (technical) features, namely: 1) authenticity of the origin of the invoice; 2) integrity of content (ensured by electronic signature); 3) standard format (readability of the file); 4) storage (access to the archive and information where the archive is stored) [6]. It should be noted that these are general rules for the validation of e-invoices in all the EU Member States provided for by Directive 2014/55/EU [10]. A more detailed analysis of the tax information contained in the invoices is carried out during the tax audit, for that in Italy, for example, VAT taxpayers are mandated to preserve the electronic invoices for at least 10 years. Cancellation of electronic invoice registration is provided only if the buyer rejects it. As a preventive measure regarding the operation of VAT fraud schemes, fines are applied: 1) 90-180% of the relevant VAT amount – for not issuing an electronic invoice or for issuing an invoice that does not comply with the XML format; 2)

100% of the relevant VAT amount – for issuing an invoice to the client that does not comply with the requirements of the Mandate [15]; 3) from 2 to 400 Euros – for each non-compliant cross-border invoice.

In other EU Member States, the introduction of e-invoicing in **France** started with business-to-government (B2G) transactions for which the national invoicing portal *Chorus Pro* was implemented. In September 2021, France approved the Mandate [9], the norms of

which provide for the following deadlines for the introduction of mandatory electronic invoicing and reporting for all B2B and B2C format transactions, depending on the size of the company (Table 3). But from July 2024 all companies (private and public) must be able to accept electronic invoices [21]. Thus, the scope of e-invoicing in France includes transactions B2B, B2C, Exports and imports transactions, Payment status of VAT invoices, Imports of services, Exports excluded.

Table 3

Terms of introduction of mandatory e-Invoicing and e-Reporting in France [21]

Companies	Terms
Large companies	as from 1 July 2024
Mid-sized companies (MSC) *	as from 1 January 2025
Small and medium enterprises (SME) **	as from 1 January 2026

* MSCs – companies which are not SMEs and have fewer than 5,000 employees and an annual turnover not exceeding EUR 1,500 million or a balance sheet total not exceeding EUR 2,000 million.

** SMEs – companies with fewer than 250 employees and an annual turnover not exceeding EUR 50 million or a balance sheet total not exceeding EUR 43 million.

In order to extend the e-invoicing system to the private sector, France introduced a Mexican model, involving the certified intermediaries whose role is to create, verify and send electronic invoices to Chorus Pro [3]. So taxpayers will be able to send e-invoices directly through the public invoicing portal (*le portail public de facturation, PPF*) from the Chorus Pro public platform, or through “dematerialization platforms” (*Plateformes de dématérialisation parteniers, PDP*), which are approved agents, or through dematerialization operators (OD). It is also provided that taxpayers will be able to mix these different e-invoicing options by choosing the PDP/OD/PPF depending on the invoice format.

One of the key objectives of implementing total e-invoicing is to combat VAT fraud by providing Continuous Transaction Control (CTC). CTC is a continuous computerized tax audit based on the processing of a critical mass of invoices, data and statuses in real time. Thus, in contrast to the Italian model, the validation of electronic invoices is not fully centralized, but is carried out either by the PPF if the taxpayer sends the invoice directly through the public invoicing portal, or by dematerialization platforms (PDP), which clean electronic invoices. That is, such PDP have the role of guarantor of the authenticity, reliability, compliance and integrity of the electronic invoice for the tax administrations. Also, as a preventive measure, the French government also imposes penalties of EUR 15 for each e-invoice not issued, but not exceeding EUR 15,000 per year for taxpayers and EUR 45,000 per year for certified PDP agents [3].

In **Spain**, since 2015, all VAT payers carrying out B2G transactions and the amount of these transactions exceeds EUR 5,000 are obliged to send electronic invoices to counterparties using Facturax XML and the national platform for the exchange of electronic invoices FACe (Punto General de Entrada de Facturas Electrónicas, PGEFe) [30]. All other transactions (e.g. non-B2G transactions or transactions under EUR 5,000) can also be sent using the platform, but this is not mandatory. At the same time, in July 2017, Spain introduced the mode of transmission of invoices to tax authorities in real time by SII. But it should be noted

that the development of e-invoicing in Spain is taking place by analogy with the Italian Mandate [15] and the French Mandate [9] and under the Law "Creation and Growth of Companies" adopted at the end of 2021, electronic invoicing will be mandatory for transactions B2B in the domestic market, namely: from 2024 – for companies and self-employed persons with an annual turnover of more than EUR 8 million; from 2026 – all other companies and freelancers. This decision was driven by aspirations aimed at increasing the efficiency of business operations and combating VAT fraud.

In order to carry out tax audits, the Spanish Tax Administration (AEAT) has access to or requests information from any participant of the VAT transaction, including the software developer [7]. Also, e-invoicing systems must meet the following requirements: 1) data protection (blocking any changes to information contained in invoices after they are issued); 2) access of the AEAT to the database in real time, which allows tracking and extraction of data registered in the system; 3) availability of an event register, which performs automatic registration of all events in the information system, which can be transferred electronically to the AEAT upon request; 4) automatic and instant reporting of all invoice registers for the AEAT [14; 22]. Invoices must contain an alphanumeric identification code, QR code, and a narrative "VERI*FACTU", which certifies that the invoice was generated using a certified (meets the technical and functional requirements provided by the AEAT) computer system and is a confirmation of the authenticity of its origin and integrity [22]. It is also mandatory to keep electronic invoices for at least 6 years. As in the practice of Italy, in the Spanish e-invoicing system cancellation of the registration of an electronic invoice is provided for only if it is rejected by the buyer.

In **Poland**, taxpayers will be obliged to issue electronic B2B invoices from July 1, 2024, and VAT-exempt taxpayers from January 1, 2025. At the same time, B2C transactions remain exempt. For e-invoicing, the e-mikrofirma program is used, which provides reporting and issuing of invoices to the national system of electronic invoices in Poland (*Krajowy System e-*

Fakturr, KSeF). All invoices are pre-verified by KSeF, after which they are assigned a unique identification number. Basic verification is supported by a centralized invoice clearing database – Continuous Transaction Controls (CTC). Further verification of the information contained in the invoices is carried out in the format of a tax audit, for which the Polish version of the OECD standard tax file (SAF-T) is used instead of the VAT tax return from October 1, 2020 [1]. As in the practice of other EU countries, an electronic invoice can be unregistered only if the client does not accept it.

It should be noted that to encourage the implementation of KSeF by taxpayers, the Polish authorities introduced a system of benefits: 1) accelerated VAT refund or credit for 40 days instead of 60 if the amount does not exceed PLN 3,000; 2) no requirement for confirmation of credit notes from company's clients; 3) no requirement to comply with the rules for archiving invoices in Poland [4]. Also, from July to December 2024, there will be a moratorium on imposing penalties for e-invoicing in Poland. Thus, in response to ensuring disclosure from taxpayers, the Polish authorities provide such taxpayers with bonuses, which contributes to building partnerships between taxpayers and tax administrations.

Although **Switzerland** is not a member of the EU, but it is associated with the EU through a number of bilateral agreements and accordingly, in the matter of VAT administration, it is governed by the same rules as the EU Member States. Consequently, Switzerland has been using an e-invoice system for more than 20 years, but different e-invoice standards have been used for B2G, B2B and B2C transactions. Since 2020, Switzerland has introduced a hybrid file format and trans-

formed the e-invoicing and e-reporting system by analogy with the French one. To verify electronic invoices and confirm their integrity and authenticity, the Swiss Federal Tax Administration (SFTA) applied the safe harbour rule, which provides that for any signs of risk, the taxpayer has the opportunity to confirm the authenticity of e-invoices. For this, the taxpayer has the opportunity to provide the SFTA with any other documents related to all processes from the purchase to the payment of the goods/service "...such as underlying contracts, order sheets, bills of delivery, booking records, payments and so on" [32]. But then, according to the principle of free consideration of evidence (contained in article 81 (3) of the Swiss VAT Law), the SFTA switched to the internal control system on procure-to-pay, which provides for the taxpayer to use the "...constant and reliable audit system a trail between procurement process, e-invoice and payment" [32], which on a permanent basis ensures the reliability and integrity of the information contained in electronic invoices. If the "safe harbour" principle is related to the one used by the Ukrainian tax administration, then the internal control system on procure-to-pay is an approach that can become a guideline for improving the Ukrainian e-invoicing system.

As a result of the generalization of the European practice of e-invoicing and its comparison with the Ukrainian practice of VAT administration using the Unified Register (Table 4), the key features of both systems, as well as the advantages and "weaknesses" of the Ukrainian practice were identified, which made it possible to formulate promising directions for improving the Ukrainian system with the aim of levelling existing shortcomings or "distortions" and bringing it closer to European practice.

Table 4

Comparative analysis of the parameters of the functioning of the Automatic VAT administration system in Ukraine and the e-Invoicing in the EU

Characteristics	Automatic VAT administration system in Ukraine	e-Invoicing in the EU
1. Issue of electronic invoices	Obligation to form an electronic VAT invoice	The payer chooses a paper or electronic form of VAT invoice
2. The range of VAT taxpayers who are required to issue electronic VAT invoices	All VAT taxpayers – legal entities and entrepreneurs	It depends on the requirements of the national legislation of a particular Member State, but mostly these are large companies
3. The range of transactions for which an electronic tax invoice is issued	All types of VAT taxpayer transactions	All VAT transactions (B2B, B2B cross-border, B2G, B2C), some exempted transactions and some non-taxed transactions
4. Registration of an electronic VAT invoice	Mandatory registration of an electronic VAT invoice	Mandatory use of e-invoices and their registration is determined by the law of Member States
5. Application of special VAT accounts	Used as a guarantee of the solvency of the VAT taxpayer in terms of paying tax obligations for the reporting month	Not applicable. The justification is that the separation of the taxpayer's capital into a separate account controlled by the state will contradict the principles of freedom of entrepreneurial activity
6. Verification of VAT invoices	The information entered in the electronic VAT invoices is used to analyze the riskiness of the VAT taxpayer, his counterparties and the riskiness of transactions, on the basis of which a decision is made to stop or refuse to register the invoice (equal to refusal in recognition of the validity of the transaction)	E-invoices are verified for authenticity and completeness
7. The right for deduction	The tax administration has the right to stop or refuse the registration of a VAT invoice, which means delaying or depriving the buyer of the right to a VAT deduction	The right to VAT deductions is a key right of a VAT taxpayer, which is embedded in the essence of the principle of neutrality of VAT taxation
8. Use of the database, risk management	The Unified Register is one of the key information sources for tax risk management. On the basis of available information, the operating system of tax administrations can visualize supply schemes involving risky taxpayers. The results of such an investigation are the basis for forming a schedule of tax audits.	In some Member States the information from the database is used to generate preliminary VAT reporting and to conduct tax audits, identify fraudulent VAT schemes and combat VAT evasion or avoidance.

Even such comparative analysis of electronic VAT administration models in Ukraine and in the EU allows us to conclude that the Ukrainian system is burdensome both for the tax administration and especially for taxpayers. As we can see from the data in Table 2, the biggest difference in the practice of e-invoicing in Ukraine and the EU is in the process of verifying VAT invoices and ensuring the taxpayer's right to a VAT deduction. If in European practice the right of a VAT taxpayer to VAT deduction is inviolable, then in Ukrainian practice such a right of a taxpayer (through the mechanism of suspension / refusal to register a VAT invoice) is used as a tool to combat VAT fraud (with schemes of minimization or non-payment of VAT), which violates the fundamental principles of VAT taxation.

It should be noted that among EU Member States there is a practice of applying repressive measures to

limit the economic consequences of VAT fraud, which is regulated by Article 273 of the VAT Directive [34]. Thus, the most common repressive tool for combating VAT fraud among the EU countries is the application of the principle of solidarity responsibility with third parties who knew about the fact of VAT evasion or avoidance (Article 205, VAT Directive) [34]. But in view of the Ukrainian practice, the effectiveness of the application of the mentioned principle is not considered promising, if this third party is the VAT taxpayer and is the main beneficiary of the VAT fraud and is the initiator of such a scheme (the scheme of forming a fictitious VAT deductions is a common scheme of fraud in Ukraine). The EU countries also use denial of the right to deduction, denial of tax exemption, or denial of VAT refund as methods of combating VAT evasion schemes. But these methods are based on the results of applying

risk-oriented tools or conducting the tax inspection, that is, the VAT taxpayer remains the specified type of right only if there is evidence of his violation of tax rules. At the same time, as a justification for their decision, tax administrations are guided by the criteria of compliance of the transaction participant, his potential and resources to the parameters of a specific transaction, while in Ukrainian practice, the verification of VAT invoices is based on a set of calculated indicators which characterized the average trend in the activity of the participant(s) and includes the payment of not only VAT, but also other taxes and fees, which cannot be considered an objective assessment. In this regard, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) insists that tax administrations must have clear and objective evidence that a specific VAT transaction has a connection with the implementation of a VAT evasion or avoidance scheme and the VAT taxpayers, who are parties to this transaction, knowingly take part in this kind of transactions.

Another aspect of the application of tools to combat VAT fraud in the Ukrainian practice of electronic VAT administration is the inclusion of a VAT taxpayer in the list of risky taxpayers, if his counterparty is recognized as risky. In the context of this issue, the CJEU ruled that the tax administration should not require the VAT taxpayer to use methods of verification of its counterparties (conducting a detailed check of its activities), which can only be carried out by the tax administration and applied during the tax audit, in order to prove his right to VAT deduction [34]. Thus, in our opinion, it is unfair to use repressive methods against the taxpayer for the illegal actions of his counterparty. The VAT taxpayer does not have the opportunity and the right to control the actions of other business entities, and therefore he cannot predict the moment of fulfilment of the conditions for applying sanctions against him and manage the factors that ensure the appearance of these conditions (principle of certainty and simplicity). Also, such a repressive method leads to the application of the presumption of fraud, which violates the principle of proportionality and cannot contribute to building partnerships between taxpayers and tax administrations.

Thus, summarizing the above, it can be stated that the Ukrainian system works according to the principle that the taxpayer may lose the right to VAT deduction at any time, in particular, when the taxpayer's participation in VAT evasion or avoidance schemes is not detected and proven. According to the author, the reason for the transformation of electronic VAT administration and risk-based tax control into a discriminatory mechanism against taxpayers in Ukraine is five aspects of the work of the Ukrainian electronic VAT administration system:

1) the moment of application of the repressive method in the form of refusal to VAT deduction – the moment of registration of the VAT invoice, i.e. the moment of fulfilment of the duty of the VAT taxpayer;

2) mismatch between the subject whose level of risk is assessed for the purpose of making a decision on the registration of the VAT invoice and the subject who is the carrier of the repressive measure – the decision to

suspend or refuse the registration of the VAT invoice is taken by the tax authority based on the analysis of data on the VAT taxpayer (seller), but as a result, the VAT taxpayer (buyer) loses the right to VAT deduction;

3) the content of the indicators that are used to determine the riskiness of the VAT taxpayer and transactions – some of them are of a general and abstract nature, others relate to the payment of other taxes (in this case, we consider it incorrect to deprive the VAT taxpayer of the right to VAT deduction for violating the payment rules other taxes than VAT). The indicators do not meet the goals of risk management and accordingly do not allow fulfilling the tasks assigned to them;

4) involvement of a large number of participants in the decision-making process regarding the status of VAT invoice registration – tax administrations create commissions to evaluate additional information provided by the taxpayer to confirm their risklessness and/or credibility of the tax transaction, as well as taxpayers are forced to engage tax lawyers or go to court for to defend their right to a VAT deduction or the right to fulfil the taxpayer's duty (however paradoxically). This increases the cost of VAT administration both on the part of tax authorities and on the part of VAT taxpayers, thereby reducing the economic efficiency and feasibility of such control measures;

5) the use of special accounts and the conditional balance on this account as a restrictive mechanism for the fulfilment by VAT taxpayers (sellers) of their duty to register a VAT invoice and the use by the VAT taxpayer (buyer) of the legal right to VAT deduction.

The presence of the above-mentioned aspects in the work of the electronic VAT administration system in Ukraine not only does not allow to simplify and speed up the VAT administration process both from the side of the tax administration and from the side of VAT taxpayers, but also creates additional, "artificial" barriers for taxpayers to fulfil their obligations regarding the payment of VAT and conducting business. Considering the fact that precisely these aspects contradict the principles that guide the EU in VAT taxation, the need for their presence in Ukrainian electronic VAT administration system raises doubts.

3.3. Proposals for improving the Ukrainian VAT electronic administration system based on European practice

According to the reports of the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine on the implementation of indicators of the budget of Ukraine, VAT is the largest source for filling the budget of Ukraine, and the efficiency of VAT administration is a key issue in ensuring the financial stability (minimization of fiscal risks) of the country's budget. The electronic system of VAT administration is a key supporting element of the VAT mechanism of taxation, accordingly, the effectiveness of VAT taxation as a whole depends on the efficiency of this system. But the presence of a large number of contradictory points in the functioning of this system does not contribute to the achievement of the main goals of VAT administration, and does not provide an opportunity to effectively combat VAT fraud. Therefore, as a response to the identified and systematized shortcomings in the functioning of the Ukrainian system of electronic VAT

administration, we have formulated the following proposals for improving the electronic system of VAT administration in Ukraine, which are listed below.

1. *The moment of application of the repressive method.* Given that at the time of making a decision on registration, suspension of registration or refusal to register a VAT invoice, the tax administration does not have sufficient information and evidence of illegal actions of the VAT taxpayer, we believe that the use of tools to "punish" taxpayers is unethical, incorrect and unfounded. Prior to this, if we are talking about the implementation of the principle of compliance of the measure of punishment with the level of guilt of the taxpayer (principle of proportionality), when the measure is determined in accordance with the violation committed by the taxpayer and does not significantly exceed it, then the application of a single format of punishment in the form of blocking the registration of the VAT invoice is disproportionately, which has a discriminatory nature in relation to honest taxpayers. Therefore, in order to preserve the risk-oriented nature of the electronic VAT administration system and foresee the application within its limits of tools to combat VAT fraud, it is necessary to expand the areas of application of the VAT database and improve the analytical tools used by tax administrations to process information from the VAT database. The mechanism of blocking the registration of tax invoices based on the existing approach should be cancelled or the point of application of this repressive method should be shifted to the moment when the tax administration has evidence of the use of minimization or evasion schemes by the taxpayer. This opinion is supported by the position of the CJEU, according to which "...the right to deduct VAT is fundamental and this right could not be denied in the presence of simple undemonstrated suspicions from the tax administration" [34]. That is, the moment of application of repressive methods must coincide in time either with the moment of committing an offense (to function as a preventive tool), or with the moment of proving the fact that the taxpayer is a participant in the VAT fraud scheme. Under such conditions, the system of electronic VAT administration will be more objective, fair and transparent, and will also be understandable and acceptable to taxpayers, which will be able to contribute to reducing the level of corruption in this system, thereby ensuring an increase in the level of taxpayers' trust in tax authorities administrations and mutual compliance.

2. *Application of repressive methods to some VAT taxpayers based on assessment of the riskiness of others.* It is also important to ensure the compliance of the VAT taxpayer, whose activity is verified with tax information, and the VAT taxpayer, whose activity is directly affected by the VAT invoice blocking mechanism. Although the use of control methods through third parties is widespread in the tax control, in this case it is not control, but the formation of grounds for the use of repressive methods. In order to restore the balance and logical connection in the format "committing an illegal act – receiving a punishment", we again appeal to the application of refusal to register a VAT invoice only when the tax administration has clear reasons to believe that the VAT taxpayer is a conscious

participant of VAT avoidance or evasion schemes. As for the information base for the formation of the evidence base, the end-to-end, cross verification should be used here, but this should take place within the scope of the tax audit (so that the audit could reveal the concrete fact of the use of a fraudulent scheme) in real time or in the format of an inspection, and not be applied during the fulfilment by the VAT taxpayer of his duties regarding the registration of the VAT invoice as a key condition of this registration.

3. *Content of risk management indicators.* At the same time, an important aspect is the review of the list of indicators used by the tax administration to assess the level of riskiness of the VAT taxpayer and the transactions he carries out or participates in. Such a review should be aimed at excluding indicators that characterize the payment of taxes other than VAT, and indicators that, according to the method of their calculation, are generally informative, but the taxpayer has a high probability of falling into the "risk" zone for this indicator, even under the condition of normal conducting activities. The list of indicators used to assess the riskiness of the VAT taxpayer or transactions should be more detailed and extensive, contain indicators that allow for a comprehensive assessment of the VAT taxpayer's activities, and be applied within the scope of tax control (audit).

4. *Significant influence of the human factor on decision-making.* Another aspect, which is directly related to the previous one, is the active and widespread use of modern technologies and the minimization of the human factor in the process of functioning of the electronic VAT administration system. This means that the VAT administration mechanism should not provide for the presence of "blind" (shadow) zones and areas, when verification of the taxpayer or transactions is carried out by tax administration officers who may have a hidden interest. Accordingly, the work of the commission which makes a decision on the registration of a VAT invoice, both at the local and central level of work of the tax administration, must be refuted. The process of making a decision based on the results of the verification of the VAT invoice (transaction) and the taxpayer can be built by analogy with the experience of risk management in the customs authorities of Ukraine, where the automated system determines the list of procedures that must be carried out in order to confirm the existence of a violation of the rules, and the customs officer based on the results of the measures taken enters into the system the information about the decision taken with a mandatory justification or notes a reasoned explanation about the impossibility of carrying out this or that control measure (this information with the designation of the customs officer is stored in the database of the customs). This approach, on the one hand, will increase the level of responsibility of tax administration officers for the decisions made, which will contribute to the minimization of the subjective/corruption component in the VAT administration system in Ukraine, and on the other hand, will lead to a decrease in the number of court cases regarding unjustified blocking of VAT invoice registration. All in all, this will contribute to reducing the cost of the VAT administration process

both on the part of tax authorities and on the part of VAT taxpayers, which fully corresponds to the principle of efficiency.

5. *Application of special VAT accounts.* It is also necessary to abandon the use of "artificial" indicators as criteria/conditions for registration of a VAT invoice, such as a conditional balance on a special VAT account. First of all, the state's withdrawal of its working capital from the taxpayer (the taxpayer loses certain economic opportunities), the state's use of these funds as an alternative source of financing its needs on interest-free terms, and at the same time the use of this account is not in the interests of the VAT taxpayer, is a distortion of economic and logical principles. Secondly, again the financial situation or the current state of payments of one VAT taxpayer (seller) should not determine the possibility of using his right to a VAT deduction for another VAT taxpayer (buyer). And as it was repeatedly stated above, any additional limitation of the VAT taxpayer's right to deduction is a gross violation of the principles of VAT taxation.

Thus, the use in the practice of VAT administration of a system that creates an artificial distribution of VAT taxpayers relative to their ability to fulfil their legal obligation to register a VAT invoice increases competition between taxpayers regarding the issue of proving to the tax administration their risklessness, and as well excludes part of their funds from circulation, thereby reducing the financial mobility of the taxpayer, cannot allow the state to expect a positive attitude towards such a system from the taxpayers and to contribute to increasing the conscientiousness of tax payment (that the decision-making by the taxpayer is influenced not only by the tax rate, but also by the way this tax is collected, i.e. the system tax administration). In such a situation, tax administrations have two ways to ensure compliance with tax rules – either increase coercive pressure on taxpayers by increasing the scope of the use of "punitive" tools, or liberalize the tax administration system, making it more convenient and understandable (in particular, decision-making algorithms) for taxpayers, such that does not violate the key rights and obligations of taxpayers. We share the opinion of Shwabii K. [29] that, especially given the need to restore the country's economy after the end of military operations on the territory of Ukraine, it is important to implement the second scenario, aimed at creating partnership relations between the state and business and forming a favourable investment climate in country.

4. Conclusions. Considering the fact that the electronic VAT administration system in Ukraine forms a large database of all transactions of a large number of taxpayers, which provides tax administrations with the opportunity to carry out tax control based on a risk management system, the need for the functioning of this system does not require additional evidence. But there is a question of improving the operation of this system from the point of view of forming a more transparent and fair system based on the balance of taxpayers and tax administrations interests, as well as from the point of view of bringing national practice closer to the standards, principles and methods of VAT administration of the European Union.

Thus, the mechanism for blocking the registration of VAT invoices in the system of electronic VAT administration in Ukraine is a tool based on the risk management system, the purpose of which is to deter or prevent the use by VAT taxpayers of various schemes that lead to the avoidance or evasion of VAT payment, to the manipulation of budget compensation, "scrolls", preventing the operation of conversion centres that create a fictitious right to VAT deduction, etc. But at the same time, the operation of the specified mechanism, as it was said earlier, violates the rights of taxpayers. Accordingly, the expediency of having this mechanism in the "European version" of the electronic VAT administration system in Ukraine should be questioned. And instead of that to find a new mechanism for punishing VAT taxpayers for violating tax legislation, the effect of which will be more objective and fair, and which not to create additional obstacles for the VAT taxpayers activity.

Taking into account the fact that the Ukrainian practice of combating various types of fraudulent schemes, and in particular VAT evasion schemes, proves the importance and necessity of using "built-in" tools to counter the illegal behaviour of VAT taxpayers, which are effective at the time of the transaction (as a preventive method) and make it impossible to carry out (registration) illegal or risky transactions. But such tools should be objective and transparent, not disrupt the normal process of doing business and not divert the attention of business owners from business development to proving the validity of their transactions to the tax administration. And despite the fact that European legislation does not restrict Member States from using various preventive measures or tools to combat VAT fraud, Ukraine should still refrain from using tools that are too "repressive" in relation to taxpayers. Moreover, the CJEU declares that the administrative measures of Member States should not exceed the limit necessary to achieve the goal of VAT administration (i.e. the combat against VAT fraud) and should not harm the activities of VAT taxpayers [34].

The improvement of the Ukrainian system of electronic VAT administration should involve the complete rejection of the use of tools that violate the rights of taxpayers or create obstacles to their business, and the wider use of such technologies as blockchain and artificial intelligence for the verification of VAT taxpayers and transactions regarding their degree of risk. The features and prospects of using modern technologies in the system of electronic VAT administration are considered by the author as a topic for further research work.

References:

1. Asquith, R. (2022). Poland SAF-T JPK_VAT updates. VATCalc, March 30, 2022. URL: https://www.vatcalc.com/poland/poland-replaces-vat-return-with-saf-t-jpk_vat-october-2020/
2. Asquith, R. (2023). EU VAT in the Digital Age ViDA – April 2023 update. VATCalc, April 5, 2023. URL: <https://www.vatcalc.com/eu/eu-vat-in-the-digital-age-vida-adopted-by-ec/>
3. Asquith, R. (2023). France B2B e-invoicing & B2C e-reporting July 2024 – pilot details. VATCalc,

- March 15, 2023. URL: <https://www.vatcalc.com/france/france-vat-b2b-e-invoicing-b2c-e-reporting-july-2024-update/>
4. Asquith, R. (2023). Poland mandatory B2B KSeF e-invoices July 2024 – update. VATCalc, March 17, 2023. URL: <https://www.vatcalc.com/poland/poland-mandatory-b2b-ksef-e-invoices-delay-to-july-2024/>
 5. Asquith, R. (2023). Spanish mandatory B2B e-invoices July 2024 – public consultation. VATCalc, March 7, 2023. URL: <https://www.vatcalc.com/spain/spanish-mandatory-b2b-e-invoices-january-2024-update/>
 6. Bakker, N. (2021). What Is E-Invoicing Compliance? – A Detailed Guide. Storecove, December 02, 2021. URL: <https://www.storecove.com/blog/en/e-invoicing-compliance/>
 7. Bakker, N. (2022). Everything You Need to Know About E-Invoicing Compliance in Spain. Storecove, April 24, 2022. URL: <https://www.storecove.com/blog/en/einvoicing-spain/>
 8. Charlet, A., & Buydens, S. (2009). VAT and GST Refunds. *The Tax Journal*, 9 March 2009, p. 21 – 23.
 9. Conseil des ministres. France (2021). *Compte rendu du Conseil des ministres du 15 septembre 2021*. September 15, 2021. URL: <https://www.gouvernement.fr/conseil-des-ministres/compte-rendu-du-conseil-des-ministres-du-15-09-2021>
 10. Council Directive 2006/112/EC of 28 November 2006 on the common system of value added tax. Current consolidated version: 01/07/2022. URL: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32006L0112>
 11. de la Feria, Rita. EU VAT Principles as Interpretative Aids to EU VAT Rules: The Inherent Paradox (December 18, 2015). In M. Lang et al (eds), *Recent VAT Case Law of the CJEU* (Linde, 2016), Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2718107> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2718107>
 12. Directive 2014/55/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on electronic invoicing in public procurement. URL: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2014/55/oj>
 13. Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, (2022). Commission proposes measures to bring VAT into the Digital Age. *European Commission*, 8 December 2022. URL: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/news/commission-proposes-measures-bring-vat-digital-age-2022-12-08_en
 14. E-invoicing in Spain: one step forward with draft proposal on technical requirements for invoicing. Marosa. URL: <https://marosavat.com/e-invoicing-in-spain-technical-invoicing/>
 15. Fatturazione elettronica e dati fattura transfrontaliere (Esterometro): Specifiche tecniche versione 1.7.1 – utilizzabili a partire dal 1 ottobre 2022. Ministero dell'Economia e delle finanze. URL: <https://www.agenziaentrate.gov.it/portale/web/guest/specifiche-tecniche-versione-1.7.1>
 16. Jones, Alice (2022). Taxpayers await EU public consultation on standardising e-invoicing. *International Tax Review*; London, Jan 19, 2022. URL: <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2630692809?accountid=29104&forcedol=true>
 17. Kaliontzoglou, A., Boutsis, P. & Polemi, D. eInvoke: Secure e-Invoicing based on web services. *Electron Commerce Res* 6, 337–353 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-006-8678-6>
 18. OECD (2017), *International VAT/GST Guidelines*, OECD Publishing, Paris. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264271401-en>
 19. OECD (2011), *OECD International VAT/GST Guidelines: Guidelines on Neutrality*. Committee on Fiscal Affairs, 28 June 2011, p. 10. URL: <https://www.oecd.org/tax/consumption/guidelinesneutrality2011.pdf>
 20. Official website of the State Tax Service of Ukraine. Results of activity: State of consideration of court cases (as of 01.01.2023). URL: <https://tax.gov.ua/diyalnist/-rezalt/644328.html>
 21. Onken, G. (2021). An UPDATE on CTCs in France: E-Invoicing and E-Reporting Mandates Postponed to July 2024. *SEEBURGER Business Integration Suite (BIS)*, 27 September 2021. URL: <https://blog.seeburger.com/an-update-on-ctcs-in-france-e-invoicing-and-e-reporting-mandates-postponed-to-july-2024/>
 22. Onken, G. (2022). Spain Approves Draft Bill for Compulsory B2B E-Invoicing. *SEEBURGER Business Integration Suite (BIS)*, 26 September 2022. URL: <https://blog.seeburger.com/spain-approves-draft-bill-for-compulsory-b2b-e-invoicing/>
 23. On making changes to the Procedure for Electronic Administration of Value Added Tax: Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated December 30, 2015 No. 1177. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1177-2015-%D0%BF#Text>
 24. On the approval of procedures for the suspension of tax invoice registration / calculating adjustments in the Unified Register of Tax Invoices: Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 11.12.2019 No. 1165 (with additions and changes dated 11.01.2023). URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1165-2019-%D0%BF#Text>
 25. On the preliminary report of the Temporary Investigative Commission of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine on the investigation of facts published in the mass media about possible corrupt actions by officials of state authorities, which led to significant losses of the revenue part of the State Budget of Ukraine: Resolution of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine dated December 2, 2020 No. 1034- IX. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1034-20#Text>
 26. Ovsienko, Margo (2021). *Complete Guide to EU VAT Invoice Requirements*. InvoiceOcean, 2021-02-12. URL: <https://invoiceocean.com/complete-guide-to-eu-vat-invoice-requirements>
 27. Owens, J. (2011). Improving performance of VAT systems is a priority in the context of the economic crisis. *World Commerce Review*, Volume 5 Issue 3, September 2011, p. 8-10. URL: https://worldcommercereview.com/publications/article_pdf/468

28. Resolution No. 1246 of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated December 29, 2010 "On approval of the Procedure for maintaining the Unified Register of Tax Invoices", as amended by Resolution No. 341 of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated April 26, 2017 (with additions and changes dated April 23, 2021). URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1246-2010-%D0%BF#Text>

29. Shwabii, K. (2023). A conscientious person will pay twice. Business Censor, February 7, 2023. URL: https://mbiz.censor.net/columns/3398083/sumlinnyy_zaplatyt_dvichi

30. Smith, W. (2023). E-Invoicing in Spain. Eco-sio. Last update 03.03.2023. URL: <https://eco-sio.com/en/blog/e-invoicing-in-spain/>

31. Stanley-Smith, Joe (2019). VAT e-invoicing uniformity would make our lives easier. International Tax Review; London (May 28, 2019). URL: <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2249628828?accountid=29104&forcedol=true>

32. Suter, B. (2016). Switzerland: VAT and e-invoicing: Switzerland back on track. International Tax Review; London, Feb 1, 2016. URL: <https://www.proquest.com/docview/1772081637?accountid=29104&forcedol=true&forcedol=true>

33. The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (2010). Tax Code of Ukraine. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2755-17#Text>

34. Traversa, E., & Ceci, E. (2023). Delimiting the margin of maneuver of tax administrations in fighting VAT fraud. Conference "Court of Justice of the European Union: Recent VAT Case Law" WU (Vienna University of Economics and Business) (January 18-20, 2023).

35. Vidhya, B., & Ravishankar, K. (2020). Italy E-invoicing using FatturaPA Standard. IBM Supply Chain Community: October 28, 2020. URL: <https://community.ibm.com/community/user/supply-chain/blogs/vidhya-b1/2020/10/28/italy-e-invoicing-using-fatturapa-standard>